

Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)

ISSN (E): 2305-9249 ISSN (P): 2305-9494

Publisher: Centre of Excellence for Scientific & Research Journalism, COES&RJ LLC

Online Publication Date: 1st October 2019

Online Issue: Volume 8, Number 4, October 2019

<https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2019.8.4.574.593>

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development of Universities' students and their attitudes towards the Islamic world issues

Field study on a sample of students of Jadara University in Irbid - Jordan

Asst. Prof. Dr. Rassmiyah Alshogran

Jadara University, Jordan

Abstract:

The study aims to explain the impact of social media publications on enhancing the knowledge of students of Jadara University and developing their knowledge on various issues. The study adopts the analytical descriptive approach in addressing the results of the study, which is reached through the questionnaire, targeting 530 students of Jadara University, So the research had reached some conclusions;

The Facebook and Whatsapp networks are the most popular social networking sites used by university students to follow up the news and issues of the Islamic world.

2. The most followed-up issues are the economic situation, then the Palestinian cause, while the less followed-up issues are the situation in Lebanon and Afghanistan.

3. The university students has learned through social networks about the Western and European countries' reality and intentions towards Turkey and the Islamic world.

Keywords:

social networks, cognitive development, trends, students of Jadara University, issues of the Islamic world, Irbid

Citation:

Alshogran, Rassmiyah (2019); Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development of Universities' students and their attitudes towards the Islamic world issues: Field study on a sample of students of Jadara University in Irbid -

Jordan; Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS), Vol.8, No.4, pp:574-593;
<https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2019.8.4.574.593>.

Methodological Framework for Research

Introduction

The increase in social networks is unstoppable and continues to bring people together with in different parts of the world through a virtual space leading to erase borders between countries. There are many social networks which attracted a wide variety of people. Human and natural events in the world played a prominent role in defining networks as they became interactive and synchronous, and were credited with delivering news to a large segment of people around the world through text messages and video clips about these events and issues. Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and other social networks are considered leaders in the new ways of communication between people around the world.

These networks have been able to break information monopoly and make it to public authorities very difficult to control access to information or containment within certain limits. Networks have the potential to bring and promote information from various sources and to communicate with them to verify their credibility and objectivity. This lead networks to play many roles such as political, economic and social adding to that their huge influence of hour to hour events as it deals with information and news at the moment of their occurrence. Many people believe that the recent events in Arab and Islamic and Western countries confirmed the strong role of these networks at the political level.

The importance of these social networks has increased accompanied with an increasing number of followers and new subscribers, especially in the Arab world, and thus the abundance of information on various issues in the Arab and Islamic world, and this strengthens the user's attitudes, including university students, about these issues and matters. In this research, the researcher will focus on the impact of social networks in students attitudes towards this and the information provided by social networks on issues that were the basis for which a particular direction was adopted.

Research Problem

Social networks today represent a global communication portal that has brought the distance and people together to exchange their conversations, issues, problems and solutions, and become a global forum for information and knowledge of many aspects of knowledge in human life. It is for people works as a meeting station, human development and the acquisition of some life skills, therefore, it influences the enhancement of user knowledge on various issues.

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development

This promotion will certainly be relative, and the level of attendance of some issues will be relatively proportional to the interests and follow-up of individuals.

Research objectives:

The aim of the research is to demonstrate the impact of social media posts on enhancing the knowledge of university students and developing their knowledge on various issues such as:

The most social networks used by the study sample to follow the news and issues of the Islamic world.

The most prominent issues of the Islamic world that the respondents follow on the social networks.

Knowledge that social networks developed in the study sample on the issues of the Islamic world.

Trends of the study sample on the issues of the Islamic world through social networks.

Research importance:

The importance of this research is to contribute to enriching studies on the phenomenon of using social networks as one of the modern technological means, and the extent of their direct effects in the culture of individuals and their attitudes towards the various issues, whether in the events in the immediate vicinity of society or the world in general, which led the study to shed light on this phenomenon and to verify the extent to which university students benefit from the use of social networks and their impact on their attitudes towards these issues in the Arab and Islamic world.

Research questions

What are the most social networks that respondents follow to know about the news and issues of the Islamic world?

What are the most prominent issues of the Islamic World that the respondents follow on the social networks?

What knowledge have social networks developed among respondents on issues related to the Islamic world?

What are the attitudes of the respondents about the issues of the Islamic world that they followed through the social networks?

Research Hypothesis

There is a direct correlation between social networks posts, knowledge development and attitudes of university students on various issues in the Islamic world.

Research terms

Social networks: A system of electronic networks that allows people to create a site of his own, and then connect it through an electronic social system with other members who have the same interests and hobbies or gathering with friends from the university or secondary school (Radi, 2003, p. 23).

Cognitive development: The practices adopted to facilitate individual growth and mental functioning for those who suffer from special cognitive deficiencies and cognitive treatments to correct the deficiencies resulting from the factors that hindered that growth or mental activity (Al Sadoki, 2012).

Cognitive development - is the process of motivating students and to learn about the issues of the Islamic and Arab world and raise their level of knowledge about these issues, to facilitate access to information on these issues, and to raise awareness of the importance of access to events and news and important issues in the Arab and Islamic nations.

Directions: A state of nervous or psychological preparedness which organized by the person's experience, that has a directional or dynamic impact on the individual's response to all the issues and attitudes that trigger the response (O'Keefe, 2002, p.6). It is a subjective tendency expressed by an evaluation of a given subject to one degree or another of preference or lack of preference. The evaluation refers to cognitive, affective and behavioral assessment responses, whether explicit or implicit (Eagley & Chaiken, 1993, p.1).

Issues of the Islamic world: The researcher means that all situations and events of the political, security and economic problems witnessed by the Arab and Islamic world, which took a time dimension in which it acquired a general framework and became an issue of the public opinion.

Theoretical Framework of the Research

Use and Satiated theory

Use and Satiated theory states that the public can choose the medium that it uses, as well as the contents of the medium. The use of the media means that the public's use of the means of communication is related to its needs and objectives. In the process of communication to separate the characteristics of the public is characterized by the positive, activity, conscious choice and good thinking. With the advent of communication and information technologies, the impact of these materials has increased especially at the level of use. The sources of electronic information, from the Internet, e-mail and electronic press, have enabled millions of people to obtain a lot of information from various sources. The public is positive in using these means of three levels: **selectivity**: Members choose the type of medium before exposure, which may be the Internet, chatting or using the e-mail and search for specific information through

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development

the use of available means. **Integration:** members do not arbitrarily the type of media because modern technologies have enabled users to access millions of information in a standard timeframe which requires integration with the media type. **Positivism:** It is combined after the exposure of the individual to the means of communication and sensations that follow this exposure and includes the response of members to the media message. This approach represents the theoretical basis for our research through the user's attempt to obtain information using the possibilities provided by the social networks. The user can identify the network from which the information is retrieved and also identify the information (Abdel Hamid, 2015, pp. 274-224).

Social networks:

Hofstede was one of the first researchers on the social networking sites in 1980. He pointed out the importance of these sites in social, cultural and educational communication. There are many studies that have dealt with the importance of social networking sites such as Herring (2007) which indicates the importance of social networks in the field of education because of its ability to link learning communities and to share experiences.

Social networks is defined as a system of electronic networks that allows the subscriber to create a site of his own, and then connect it through an electronic social system with other members who have the same interests and hobbies or gathered with friends of the university or secondary school (Radi, 2003, p. 23). There are a lot of social networks sites as Twitter, Facebook, Youtube, Viber, Whatsapp, Imo, Instagram, and other blogs and forums. The use of them in the search engines in billions and the need to activate them in various sectors of the society and to overcome the traditional means of communication effectively to cope with the rapid development of communication and information in the world.

Social Networks Role in Knowledge Development:

Social networks play an active role in building knowledge and in shaping trends towards various social and humanitarian issues that surround human being, or those that raise individual's interests in different countries of the world. Since the beginning of 2011, the impact of these networks in the attitudes of young people to bring about social change was clear, which means that networks provide users with information and knowledge to change and renew awareness, as well as they play a fast interactive communication channels between people.

Based on what the Arab world and the Islamic world witnessed from events and different issues; social networks had a great presence in these events in a negative and positive ways, and users found it as the best and fastest way to deliver information or promote an idea.

Many studies have confirmed that media role in guiding the public to specific issues achieves a degree of consensus on issues priorities in the society and this is one of the most prominent jobs discussed by the media in societies (Hassan, 1997).

Attitude: It is defined as a set of ideas, feelings, perceptions and beliefs about a subject, which directs an individual's behavior and determines his position on that subject, and a positive or negative inclination towards a particular issue that the individual predicts and is convinced of his or her point of view towards them (Alimat, 1994).

Therefore, the amount of information and data that individuals are exposed to contribute to the formation of their ideas and perceptions about different issues, including the political and intellectual issues and events experienced by humanity.

Literature Review

Awad (2013). The impact of social networking sites on the development of social responsibility among young people

The study aimed to examine the impact of social networks on developing social responsibility among young people through the implementation of a training program for a group of youth of Alar Youth Council. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher applied the training program to the members of the experimental group from (18) Alar Youth Council young men and women, then the researcher applied the of social responsibility measure (pre-measurement), which the researcher developed, and verified the validity and stability. The content of the program was a major goal and a number of behavioral goals that emerged from it. The program consisted of (5) meetings implemented within five days at a rate of (4) hours per meeting, and the researcher set several goals for each meeting. The researcher also used various techniques and methods of training such as acquaintance, clarification, group formation, practical training, questioning and inquiry, finishing and evaluation, lecture, group discussion and interactive games. The researcher also used various means to make the program successful, including using pens and presentations. The study showed that there were statistically significant differences between the average scores of the experimental group at the level of significance (0.05) in the level of social responsibility. Before and after the application of the program in favor of the application of the training program. The study also showed no statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) in the average scores of males and females in the experimental group at the level of social responsibility after application of the program.

Ghazal and Chaoubi (2014). The impact of social networking sites on the development of political awareness among university students.

The study aimed to uncover the social networking sites in the development of political awareness for University students of the QasidiMarbah University in Algeria through a study of a class sample of university students from the users of these sites, a questionnaire was adopted to collect data from (30) respondents, the study was divided into theoretical and practical aspects, in which the hypotheses that are themes of the questionnaire were verified. The first is the use of social networking sites, and the second axis: the use of social networking sites by students increases political awareness, and the third axis is the importance of political awareness among students. The study found the following results: The majority of the respondents spend more than three hours in the use of sites, most of them prefer to comment and chat in the first place which means to express their views freely. Most respondents use the website to communicate with family and friends and Opening the way for political debate within the virtual community. The study also found that the use of these sites affects face-to-face contact. The results of the study showed a high interest among the youth in the university in following up the international and local political issues of The Arabs. The social networks communication sites increase the development of political awareness through open debates.

Saidi and Daif (2015). The use of social networks sites and its impact on university student values . Facebook as a model.

The study aimed to detect the impact of social networking sites on students' values through a sample of (85) students of Facebook users at the University of Ouargla in Algeria, the research adapted the questionnaire to collect data on habits and patterns of using Facebook, social values and the impact of Facebook in these values. Our study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that Facebook contributed to know and understand many traditions and cultures of peoples in addition to the formation of knowledge and perceptions about the other and adversely affected their social interaction, especially with family members.

Research Methodology

This study is an analytical descriptive study; the researcher used the descriptive analytical method. This study is also one of the causal explanatory studies to examine the causal relationships between the independent variable represented by the social networks and the dependent variable that represents the cognitive development.

The community of the study

The study community is composed of (4000) students from Jadra University in the first semester 2018-2019. The researcher adopted the random sample method in selecting the sample of the study. The study sample reached (530) of them (298) male students and (232) female students. Table (1) shows the details of the study community.

Table (1)

Distribution of the study sample according to the demographic characteristics

Variable	Frequency	%	Variable	Frequency	%
Sex			Social status		
Male	298	56.23%	Single	423	79.81%
Female	232	43.77%	Married	107	20.19%
Total	530	100%	Total	530	100%
Age			Academic qualification		
18-22	286	53.96%	BA	480	90.57%
23-27	122	23.02%	Master degree	50	9.43%
28-32	92	17.36%	Total	530	100%
33- more	30	5.66%	Type of study		
Total	530	100%	Humanitarian	336	63.40%
			Scientific	194	36.60%
			Total	530	100%

Source: by the researcher based on results of statistical analysis (SPSS).

Validity and Reliability of the study

The questionnaire was presented to a number of faculty members in the Jordanian universities to verify the reliability of the paragraphs. Their opinions were taken and the necessary amendments were made to accurately balance the contents of the articles in the questionnaire paragraphs. In order to calculate the stability of the research tool, the researcher used the method of comparing the internal consistency using the Cronbach Alpha Test, where the values of Kronbach Alpha for all the variables of the search and the questionnaire in general (81%) is higher than (60%) which is acceptable in research and studies, Stability values ranged from 79.3 to 91.7.

Statistical analysis: Descriptive and analytical statistical methods were used using the SPSS. Recurrences and percentages were extracted. In order to answer the research questions, the arithmetic mean and standard deviations were used. The Kronbach alpha test was also used to confirm the stability of the research tool, Independent Sample T-test and the use of the One Way ANOVA test, and the LSD test for dimensional comparisons. The results of the descriptive statistical analysis of data, which include the arithmetical averages and standard

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development

deviations of the entire independent research theme and the constituent paragraphs of each axis, were based on the results.

Research results:

The statistical averages and standard deviations were obtained to identify the study community responses of members on "**the impact of social networks in promoting the cognitive development of university students and their orientation towards the issues of the Islamic world**".

To answer this question, the arithmetical averages and standard deviations were extracted to identify the responses of the study community members on the axis.

Table (2)

The statistical averages and standard deviations of members of the study community responses on "the most social networks used by respondents to follow the news and issues of the Islamic world" in descending order..

No.	Paragraph	arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation
1	Facebook	4.354	0.1456	1	High
2	Whatsapp	4.274	0.2140	2	High
3	Twitter	4.1235	0.3254	3	High
4	Websites	3.6547	0.22924	4	Medium
5	YouTube	3.2315	1.04476	5	Medium
6	Electronic newspapers	2.3454	1.19520	6	Medium
7	Instagram	1.9215	1.45385	7	Low
8	Snap Chat`	1.9147	1.31751	8	Low
9	Telegram	1.8905	1.37095	9	Low
10	LinkedIn	1.8123	1.05447	10	Low
11	Viber	1.8086	1.24295	11	Low
12	Tango	1.7986	1.24295	12	Low
13	Imo	1.7713	1.32116	13	Low
	Total	2.684662	0.935234		Medium

Source: by the researcher based on results of statistical analysis (SPSS).

Table (2) shows that the averages for the article (**the most popular social networks used by respondents to follow the news and issues of the Islamic world**) ranged between (4.354 and 1.7713), as it has a total arithmetic mean of (2.684662), which is of the intermediate level. Paragraph (1) has the highest mean of (4.354) and a standard deviation of (0.1456), which is from the high level. The paragraph stated that the most social network used by respondents to follow the news and issues of the Islamic world is (Facebook). In the second place

came paragraph (3) with an average of (4.274) and a standard deviation of (0.2140). It is also at the high level, as the paragraph states that the most social network used by respondents to follow the news and issues of the Islamic world is Whatsapp.

In the penultimate position, paragraph (13) came with an average of (1.7986) and a standard deviation of (1.24295) which is within the low level. The paragraph stated that the lowest social networks used by the respondents to follow the news and issues of the Islamic world is Tango at the final place, paragraph (4) came with an average of (1.7713) and a standard deviation of (1.32116), which is within the low level. The paragraph states that the lowest social networks used by the respondents to follow the news and issues of the Islamic world is Imo. This explains that Facebook and Watsapp are among the most popular social networks used by respondents to follow the news and issues of the Muslim world.

The second area: the most prominent issues of the Islamic world, which I follow on social networks.

Table (3)

The statistical averages and standard deviations of the responses of members of the study community on "the most prominent issues of the Islamic world I follow on social networks" are arranged in descending order.

No.	Paragraph	arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation
14	The economic situation in Jordan	4.8211	1.2354	1	High
17	The Palestinian issue and the Jewish policies	4.6544	0.2110	2	High
21	The security situation in Libya, Syria and Yemen	4.1235	0.3254	3	High
25	The humanitarian situation in Burma	3.8547	0.1251	4	High
22	The political and security situation in Iraq	3.8315	1.0947	5	High
18	Arab and Islamic position on the Palestinian issue	3.6414	1.1852	6	Medium
26	Issues of humanitarian asylum and illegal	3.4547	0.1251	7	Medium

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development

	migration				
15	The political situation in Turkey	2.7395	0.0947	8	Medium
16	The siege on Qatar	2.6414	0.6852	9	Medium
19	Gulf role in the Yemeni crises	2.2215	1.5385	10	Low
20	Gulf role in the Syrian crises	1.9147	1.3151	11	Low
23	the Arab and Islamic communities situations abroad	1.8905	0.3095	11	Low
24	Iranian role in the region	1.8123	0.5447	12	Low
29	The political situation in Egypt	1.6313	1.3116	15	Low
28	The political situation in Lebanon	1.7986	1.4245	14	Low
27	The security and humanitarian situation in Afghanistan	1.8086	1.2495	13	low
	Total	3.13198	0.85168	Medium	

Source: by the researcher based on results of statistical analysis (SPSS).

Table (3) shows that the themes averages (the most prominent issues of the Islamic world I follow on social networks) ranged between (4.8211 and 1.6313), where the theme gained a total average of 3.13198, and It is an intermediate level.

Paragraph (14) has the highest mean at (4.8211) and a standard deviation of (1.2354), which is from the high level, the paragraph states that one of the most prominent issues in the Islamic world that I follow on social networks is the economic situation in Jordan. In the second place came paragraph (17) with an average of (4.6544) and a standard deviation of (0.2110) which is also high. The paragraph states that one of the most prominent issues of the Islamic world I follow on the social networks is the Palestinian issue and the Jewish policies towards it. In the third place came paragraph (21) with an average of (4.1235) and a standard deviation of (0.3254). It is also within the high level. The paragraph states that one of the most prominent issues in the Islamic world that I follow on the social networks is the security situation in Libya, Syria and Yemen.

In the penultimate position, paragraph (28) came with an average of (1.7986) and a standard deviation of (1.4245) which is within the low level, The paragraph states that one of the issues of the Islamic world which I follow very little on the social networks is (the situation is the political situation in Lebanon). The last paragraph which paragraph (27) came with an average of (1.8086) and a standard deviation (1.2495) which is within the low level. The paragraph states that one of the issues of the Islamic world, which I follow little on the social networks, is the "security and humanitarian situation in Afghanistan". This explains why the respondents are intensively following the local economic situation in their country, and then they follow the status of the Palestinian issue and the events that are going on around it, while the less follow-up issues are the security situation in Lebanon and Afghanistan.

The results of the study are similar to Ghazal and Shoubi (2014) study on the impact of social networking sites on the development of political awareness among the university students. The results of the study showed high interest among the youth of the university in following up the Arab, international and local political issues. Network sites increase the development of political awareness through open debates on them.

The third area: knowledge that social networks sites have contributed in their development for the respondents on Islamic world issues.

To answer this question, the arithmetical averages and standard deviations were extracted to identify the responses of the study community members on the theme.

Table (4)

The statistical averages and standard deviations of members responses of the study community on "the most prominent knowledge that social networks have developed according to the respondents on issues of the Islamic world" ranked in descending order..

No.	Paragraph	arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation
35	I knew through social networks that the Arabs and Muslims are dispersed and their situation does not help a unified position	4.7956	0.53533	1	High
33	It showed me the truth and intentions of	4.3794	1.05665	2	High

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development

	some Western and European countries about Turkey and the Islamic world				
41	I realized that Arab and Islamic issues can only be tackled by Arabs and by Islam	4.3471	1.00667	3	High
34	I realized that most of the troubled internal political situation is due to external interference	4.3103	0.74960	4	High
36	Through which I learned that Iran is a nation-state seeking to expand in Muslim countries from the gate of religion	4.9912	0.94779	5	High
31	It provides me with many details about the political situation in Turkey	4.8853	1.03762	6	High
43	I was totally sure that the division of the Arab and Islamic is the main reason of their weakness.	3.8809	0.88960	7	High
38	I find the weakness or absence of Arab and Islamic regimes positions towards important issues	3.7441	1.08102	8	High
39	showed me the	3.5515	0.84967	9	Medium

	truth about what is going on in Syria				
40	details about the Iraq crises in terms of the political situation	3.3471	1.03410	10	Medium
32	provided me with a lot of details about the political situation in Malaysia	3.3368	1.19022	11	Medium
37	showed me the truth about what is going on in Libya	3.0118	0.93839	13	Medium
42	showed me the truth about what is going on in Yemen	2.7574	1.22982	14	Medium
44	showed me the truth about what is happening in Burma	3.1735	1.07421	12	Medium
	Total	3.7508	0.9729	Medium	

Source: by the researcher based on results of statistical analysis (SPSS).

Table (4) shows that the statistical averages of the theme (the most prominent knowledge that social networks have developed according to the respondents on issues of the Islamic world) ranged between (4.7956 and 3.1735), where the theme obtained a total arithmetic mean of (3.7508) of the intermediate level.

Paragraph (35) has the highest average score at (4.7956) and a standard deviation (0.53533). It is a high level. The paragraph stated that one of the most prominent knowledge that has developed by social networks of the respondents on Islamic world issues is (The knowledge that the Arabs and Muslims dispersed and their status does not help a unified position), and in the second place was paragraph (33) with an average of (4.3794) and a standard deviation (1.05665), the paragraph states that one of the most prominent development of social networks of the respondents on the issues of the Islamic world is (knowing the reality and intentions of some Western and European countries towards Turkey and the Islamic world). In the third place, paragraph (41) with an average of (4.3471) and a standard deviation of (1.00667) is also at the high level. The

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development

paragraph stated that one of the most prominent development of social networks of the respondents on the issues of the Islamic world is (Arab and Islamic issues can only be addressed by Arabs and Islamic people). In the penultimate position, paragraph (42) came with an average of (1.7986) and a standard deviation of (2.7574). It is within the average level. The paragraph states that the knowledge that social networks has developed among the respondents on issues of the Islamic world is less (what is happening in Yemen). At the last place, paragraph (44) came with an average of (3.1735) and a standard deviation of (1.07421). It is within the intermediate level. The paragraph states that the knowledge that social networks has developed among the respondents on issues of the Islamic world is less (The reality of what is happening in Burma). This explains that the respondents realized through the social networks that the Arabs and Muslims are dispersed and their situation does not help a unified position, and they have seen the reality and intentions of some Western and European countries towards Turkey and the Islamic world.

This study is consistent with the findings of the Saidi and Deif study (2015) on the use of social networking sites and their impact on values among university students, which showed that Facebook contributed to know many traditions and cultures of peoples in addition to the formation of knowledge and perceptions about the other.

The fourth area: Respondents attitudes to the issues of the Islamic world through social networks.

To answer this question, the arithmetical averages and standard deviations were extracted to identify the responses of the study community members on the theme.

Table (5)

The statistical averages and standard deviations of the responses of members of the study community on "trends of respondents on issues of the Islamic world through social networks", and they are arranged in descending order.

No.	Paragraph	arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Rank	Evaluation
45	I have become more supportive for the Palestinian case	3.6162	1.20188	1	High
46	It made me more sympathetic to the Turkish government	3.5000	1.11886	2	Medium
53	It made me take a negative stance on	3.4368	1.07952	3	Medium

	Iran				
48	It made me more convinced that I should have a positive role in society	3.3868	1.49879	4	Medium
49	I became more opposed to normalization with Israel	3.3735	1.31331	5	Medium
50	I support cooperation among Islamic countries (Iran, Turkey and Saudi Arabia)	2.9485	1.27811	6	Medium
26	I was prepared to interact with any national effort to support Arab and Islamic issues	2.8279	1.31764	7	Medium
54	Have become more rejecting for the interference of Arab states in each other	2.6985	1.11569	8	Medium
47	It convinced me of the right to impose a blockade on Qatar	2.2544	1.08259	9	Low
52	Made me support the position of the Syrian government dealing with the parties to the opposition militarily.	2.1206	1.02696	10	Low
	Total	3.01632	1.203335	Medium	

Source: by the researcher based on results of statistical analysis (SPSS).

Table (5) shows that the statistical averages of the theme (trends of respondents on issues of the Islamic world through social networks) ranged between (3.6162

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development

and 2.1206). The theme obtained an average of (3.01632). Paragraph (45) has the highest average score at (3.6162) and a standard deviation of (1.20188), which is a high level. The paragraph stated that one of the most prominent trends of the respondents on the issues of the Islamic world through social networks is the (Palestinian conflict). Paragraph (46) came in the second place with an average of (3.5000) and a standard deviation (1.11886), it is within the average level. The paragraph states that one of the most prominent trends of the respondents on the issues of the Islamic world through the social networks is (made me more sympathetic with the Turkish Government).

In the penultimate position, paragraph (47) came with an average of (2.2544) and a standard deviation (1.08259) which is within the low level, The paragraph states that one of the weakest attitudes towards the issues of the Islamic world through social networks is "I was convinced of the right on right of Qatar siege". In the last place, paragraph (52) came with an average of (2.1206) and a standard deviation (1.02696) which is within the low level. The paragraph stated that one of the weakest attitudes of the respondents to the issues of the Islamic world through the social networks is (made me support the position and dealings of the Syrian government with the parties of the opposition militarily and politically). This explains that the most popular attitudes promoted by users of social networks are to strengthen support for the Palestinian conflict, increase sympathy and support with Turkish policies in the region, while the results showed a lack of conviction of the blockade on Qatar and rejection of Syrian government policies with its people.

The main hypothesis: There is a direct correlation between the social networks posts, knowledge development and attitudes of university students on various issues in the Islamic world.

In order to prove the correlation hypothesis for the dimensions of the study, the correlation coefficient for the theme dimensions was calculated with the main theme in general, in addition to the level of significance, and the results were as follows:

Table (6)

The correlation between theme dimensions and the theme in general

The study tool themes	Dimensions	Correlation	Sig	Significance
-----------------------	------------	-------------	-----	--------------

The correlation between social networking posts and knowledge development and attitudes of university students on various issues in the Islamic world	Use of social networks	0.663**	0.000	statistical significance
	Developing the knowledge and attitudes of university students			

Source: by the researcher based on results of statistical analysis (SPSS).

Thus, we note that there is a positive correlation between the social networks posts and knowledge development and attitudes of university students on various issues of the Islamic world and with a correlation coefficients of (0.663 **) and statistical significance (0.00), which is less (0.05), which means accepting the hypothesis and that there is a statistically significant relation between social networks posts and the knowledge development and attitudes of university students on various issues of the Islamic world.

Conclusions and recommendations

Results: The research results are:

Facebook and Wattsapp are among the most popular social networks sites used by respondents to follow up the news and issues of the Islamic world.

The respondents are following intensively the local economic situation in their country, followed by the Palestinian conflict and the events surrounding it, while the less follow-up issues are the situation in Lebanon and Afghanistan.

The respondents realized through the social networks that the Arabs and Muslims are dispersed and their situation does not help a unified position, and they noticed, through these networks, the reality and intentions of some Western and European countries towards Turkey and the Islamic world.

This explains that the most popular attitudes promoted by the users of social networks are to strengthen the support for the Palestinian case, increase sympathy and support with Turkish policies in the region, while the results showed a lack of conviction of the blockade on Qatar and rejection of Syrian government policies with its people.

Social networks impact in promoting knowledge development

There is a positive correlation between social networks posts and the knowledge development and attitudes of university students on various issues of the Islamic world.

Recommendations:

The Arab and Islamic organizations' investment of Facebook and Whatsapp in enhancing the confidence of the Arab public in its future through the presentation of visions and practical projects for the knowledge development in the Arab countries.

To ensure that the official bodies in the Arab and Islamic countries to communicate with members of the community through the various official channels and strengthen the social networks communication.

References

Hassan, Khaled Salahuddin (1997). The role of television and journalism in directing public interest in public issues in Egypt: analytical and field study, unpublished master thesis. College of Information. Cairo University. Cairo.

Radi, Zaher (2003.) Use of social networking sites in the Arab world, Journal of Education, No. 15, Amman Private University, Amman.

Saidi, Hanan and Daif, Aisha (2015). The use of social networking sites and its impact on the values of the university student. Facebook is a model. (Master Academy Message). Department of Information and Communication Sciences, Department of Information and Communication Sciences, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Qasidi Marbah and Wargalah University.

Sadouqi, Mohamed (2012). School and the question of cognitive development. Article published at: <http://www.tanmia.ma/ar/2012-08-13-12-02-07/>

Abdul Hamid, Mohammed (2015). Information theories and trends of influence, V5. Cairo: Book World. Pp. 274-290

Alimat, Mohamed Mokbel (1994), Attitudes of secondary vocational education teachers towards the profession of education in Jordan and the impact of variables of experience, specialization and qualification, Muta for Researches and Studies, Volume 9, No. 3, pp. 77-94.

Awad, Hosny (2013). The impact of social networks sites on the development of social responsibility among young people - the experience of Allar youth council. University of Sharjah Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences. 10 (2). 2013. Sharjah. The United Arab Emirates. Pp. 101-129.

Ghazal, Marim and Shawbi, Nour Al-Huda (2014). The impact of social networks sites on the development of political awareness among the university students. (Research to complete the requirements of the BA certificate). Department of Information and Communication Sciences, Department of Human Sciences, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Qasidi University, Marabah, Ouargla, Algeria.

O'Keefe, Daniel J. (2002). Theory and Research. 2nd Edition. London ,New Delhi: Sega Publications.

Eagly, A. H., & Chaiken, S. (1993). The psychology of attitudes. Orlando, FL, US: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich College Publishers